

METHODS OF MODERN EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING OF YOUNG GRADUATES WITH VISION PROBLEMS

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Abstract. *This article is about modern methods of education and upbringing of young graduates with vision problems. Educational processes implemented in boarding schools and modern methods of education and upbringing of blind graduates are illuminated.*

Keywords: *visually impaired students, boarding school, education, educational work, modeling.*

The growth of the educational activity of each educational institution depends on educational and spiritual-upbringing activities outside the classroom. Special boarding school students are involved in various science and craft clubs, as well as educational activities, directly after the lesson. Such extracurricular activities are highly effective and have a unique positive effect on the employment and social activity of students with visual impairments, as well as on learning additional skills. In this regard, the convenience of the educational and correctional training sessions organized by the students after the lesson affects the improvement of the learner's social adaptation processes. Involvement of blind graduating students in such effective activities motivates students to develop self-service, self-help, and social communication skills.

Education is a phenomenon that encompasses socially important tasks, and it creates conditions for a person's direct contact with society. Education is a broad concept, and in its essence, it helps to bring up a person and social adaptation in interpersonal relations in a practical way.

"The famous scientist Herbert attached great importance to determining the goal of education. He believes that the goals and tasks of education are to form a person with good character. Herbart recognized intellectual education as the biggest and main means of education in the pedagogical work, and believed that there would be no education without upbringing.

"The social environment, which does not always have all-round facilities for the development and formation of a human as a person, cannot educate mature people as it is. The activities of educational institutions organized by the society and all people participating in the educational process play an important role in the education of a person. The main task of education in the development of a person is to correctly reflect the demands placed on a person by society in the way of tasks and goals of educational work, taking into account the social environment. When organizing the educational work of students at school, the teacher certainly takes into account his home conditions and home environment. Studying the students' home conditions in many cases makes it possible to analyze, correct, and prevent the negative characteristics that are formed in the child due to the upbringing environment in the family, and at the same time, to increase the positive ones.

"Educational processes in the general secondary education system are interrelated, but also consist of independent structural elements taken separately. The structural elements of education include: educational goals, tasks, factors, content, organizational forms, methods, tools and

conditions. It should be emphasized that the purpose of education is to raise a mature generation - a person who is intellectually mature, spiritually rich, and able to work productively in various sectors of the national economy of our republic.

Education is a goal-directed activity of an educator to form certain qualities and characteristics of a person, and it is always directed to a specific age group. Because, taking into account their peculiarities and capabilities, real educational tasks can be promoted and identified, defined methods and means of educational influence can be selected.

"Educational works and activities held in boarding schools are of great importance in adapting students to life. Each educational training is conducted in the areas of systematic and practical application, orientation to labor and profession, manners, refinement, hygienic, legal, ecological education.

"The effectiveness of educational activities aimed at the development of social adaptation of visually impaired students requires the fulfillment of the following conditions in order to express the relationship between the results that can be achieved and the results already achieved, to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process:

- realization of the importance and necessity of spiritual needs;
- taking into account the specific characteristics of motives during the educational process and educational relations;
- development of positive motives for students to acquire high moral qualities;
- making a creative environment that creates necessary and favorable conditions for the development of legal thinking of students;
- basing on cooperation in the education process;
- it is necessary to take into account the factors that have a positive effect on the development of legal thinking of students.

"The modeling of the educational system began in the second half of the 20th century. Management of education on the basis of a specific system ensures a clear, purposeful course of organized pedagogical activities. Many foreign and domestic pedagogues have expressed their scientific opinions about the process of educational modeling. Among the Uzbek scientists, pedagogues such as B. Suyunov, O. Tolipov, M. Usmonboyeva showed the advantages and convenient aspects of modeling technology. One of the advantages of modeling technology is the organization of educational content.

According to the essence of this technology, the available information is selected that will allow students to successfully implement their activities within the framework of state educational standards.

The essence of modeling is to design the educational process on the basis of organizing the contents of the model educational subject and its departments, dividing professional activities that cannot be divided into logically completed parts from a certain stage of education.

Then, for each model, the content and impact of the activity specific to this model is determined.

To achieve the goal of modeling technology, the model is implemented step by step. Every action taken in this process is considered as a learning element.

During the academic year, educational discussion sessions on the following topics are organized for the students of the graduating class, who are carrying out educational activities in boarding schools, according to the program determined by the group educator.

Before organizing each educational activity, as well as extracurricular activities, it is necessary to pay special attention to its content, exposure processes, and the convenience of learners with vision problems.

It is necessary that any extracurricular activities carried out in boarding schools serve to develop the social adaptation skills of blind students. As long as the students of these events do not thoroughly acquire life knowledge, the effectiveness of the work being done will not be seen. Spiritual and educational events help visually impaired students improve their speaking skills, learn stage culture, and give a speech in front of the public. For this, educational institutions are required to use typhotechnical tools, paying particular attention to the corrective purpose of the organized activities.

The comprehensive education and upbringing of visually impaired graduates directly depends on the effectiveness of the educational and extracurricular spiritual-upbringing activities organized in the educational institution.

In conclusion, the development of issues of social adaptation of visually impaired graduates directly depends on the effectiveness of educational and spiritual-upbringing activities. Self-care, self-awareness and communication with people depend on the educational knowledge, skills and abilities learned in the educational institution.

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